

A Study On Employee Grievance And Redressal Procedures In Tamilnadu State Transport Corporation Limited

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Abstract:

The personnel or industrial relations department of the organization is responsible for maintaining peace and harmony among employer and employee. The healthy relations between employer/management and employee/worker can be achieved through the agreed solutions for different problems. A worker who is dissatisfied may not work at full capacity and cause significant loss of production. Grievances are the expressed complaints about working conditions and environment in which employee work. It is related with day to day work. Grievances emerge out of the dissatisfaction of workers it may be as an individual or as a group. Thus, management strive hard to resolve workers complaints and grievances. Effective grievance handling is an essential part of cultivating good employee relations and running a fair, successful, and productive workplace. This paper examines nature and reasons of employee grievances, illustrates grievance handling procedure, and comprehends consequences of mishandling grievances at the workplace.

Catchphrases: Employer, Grievance handling procedure, Grievance handling machinery, Worker.

Introduction

Diversity at workplace is high today as employees from different age group, nationality, gender, ethnic and religious backgrounds are forming part of the workforce team. Amid this situation, miscommunication and misunderstanding are likely to happen if the diversity at workplace is not handled properly. This will also affect the employees' morale and productivity of the organization. Even, due to the technological advancement in communication media, a small problem or misunderstanding may be blown to a big issue through different social media. Such issue may affect the employers' image, which causes unnecessary embarrassment to the management. Sometimes, such grievances may also cause more expensive to the organization and also time consuming litigations. Management, need to look these types of grievances with high priority by adopting a favourable working environment and fair employment practice. It can be managed if the grievance handling procedures (GHP) are adopted properly by the organization. Both the employees and employers need to understand the nature of grievances and the ways of resolving it so as to get satisfaction by both parties. The key reason of grievance redressal procedure is not to resolve or settlement of the grievances but to maintain industrial harmony between the stakeholders.

Review Of Literature

Baldev R. Sharma and Sundararajan P.S. (1983) in their study on "Organisational Determinants of Labour Management relations in India" investigated factors determining labour management relations in 50 companies. Of the nine factors studied, the two included in the best equation scope for advancement and grievance handling were found to be the most

critical determinants. Together these two factors accounted for 58 percent of the variation in labour management relations across the 50 companies.

Menon P.K.S.(1983) in his study on "Personnel Management in Banks" examined the procedures, practices and policies prevalent in personnel administration in banks in India. He identified that behind the facade of trade unionism the bullies influenced every facet of management whether it was collective bargaining, grievance procedures, disciplinary matters, departmental enquiries or employee managerial relations.

Gordon and Miller (1984) suggested that, any item in the union contract can be the subject of a grievance. However, there is general agreement that discipline is the single most frequent issue grieved. The available grievance processing research indicates that most grievances are resolved within the first two steps of the grievance procedure, and that most of the resolutions occur within two months of the filing date (Delaney et al., 1989; Gideon and Peterson, 1979). The fact that arbitration is a relatively time consuming and expensive grievance resolution step helps explain why unions and employers use arbitration relatively sparingly.

Objective Of The Study.

1. To study the nature of grievances faced by Tamilnadu State Transport Corporation – Villupuram Division.
2. To assess the methods adopted by Tamilnadu State Transport Corporation – Villupuram Division to redress the employees grievances.
3. To find out the level of employees' awareness about labour laws adopted inside the organization.

Tools for analysis

The statistical gear was used for the cause of the evaluation of this take a look at is straightforward

percentage method . After the gathering of records via the questionnaire, editing became achieved cautiously. Based on the responses of the samples,

Analysis and Interpretation

the tables were prepared. The statistics accumulated were analyzed and interpreted with the help of tables.

Table No. 1: Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Designation of the Respondents

Designation	Frequency	Percent
Driver	175	58
Conductor	125	42
Total	300	100

Source: Primary data

Above table that Frequency and percentage distribution of the designation of the respondents are given in the above table. It is

observed that 58 percent of the respondents are drivers while the remaining 42 percent of the respondents are conductors.

Table No. 2: Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Age of the Respondents

Age	Frequency	Percent
Less than 31 years	30	10
31 to 40 years	150	50
41 to 50 years	50	17
Above 50 years	70	23
Total	300	100

Source: Primary data

Table shows frequency and percentage distribution of the age of the respondents. It is noted that majority (50%) of the respondents are in the age category of 31 to 40 years, while 23 percent of the respondents are in the age category of above 50

years, and 17 percent of the respondents are in the 41 to 50 years age group. However, 10 percent of the respondents fall under less than 31 years of age group.

Table No. 3: Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Educational Qualification of the Respondents

Educational Qualification	Frequency	Percent
School level	150	50
Diploma/Graduate	120	40
Postgraduate	30	10
Total	300	100

Source: Primary data

Frequency and percentage distribution of the educational qualification of the respondents is shown in the above table. It is observed that majority (50%) of the respondents have completed only school level of education while 40 percent of the respondents have the educational qualification of

diploma or graduation. Further it is noted that 10 percent of the respondents have hold post-graduation degree which proves that majority of the employees who work as drivers and conductors do not possess higher educational qualification.

Table No. 4: Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Marital Status of the Respondents

Marital Status	Frequency	Percent
Single	120	40
Married	180	60
Total	300	100

Source: Primary data

Table shows that frequency and percentage distribution of the marital status of the respondents. It is noted that majority (60%) of the respondents are married whereas 40 percent of the respondents

are living as singles, which shows that family commitments are more for the majority of the employees who work as conductors and drivers.

Table No. 5: Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Experience of the Respondents

Experience	Frequency	Percent
Less than 6 years	40	13
6 to 10 years	120	40
11 to 15 years	70	24
16 to 20 years	48	16
21 to 25 years	12	04
More than 25 years	10	03
Total	300	100

Source: Primary data

Frequency and percentage distribution of the experience of the respondents is shown in the above table. It is observed that majority (40%) of the respondents are having 6 to 10 years of experience, while 24 percent of the respondents are having 11 to 15 years of experience. 16 percent of the respondents are coming under 16 to 20 years of experience category and 13 percent of respondents

have less than 6 years of work experience. Further it is noted that 4 percent of the respondents have 21 to 25 years of experience, and only 3 percent of the respondents have more than 25 years of experience. Hence, it is concluded that majority of the respondents who work as drivers and conductors have more than 10 years of experience.

Table No. 6: Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Family Type of the Respondents

Family Type	Frequency	Percent
Joint family	180	60
Nuclear family	120	40
Total	300	100

Source: Primary data

Table shows that frequency and percentage distribution of the family type of the respondents. It is noted that majority (60%) of the respondents live in joint family whereas 40 percent of the respondents live as nuclear family.

Findings

It is observed that 58 percent of the respondents are drivers while the remaining 42 percent of the respondents are conductors.

It is noted that majority (50%) of the respondents are in the age category of 31 to 40 years

It is observed that majority (50%) of the respondents have completed only school level of education.

It is noted that majority (60%) of the respondents are married whereas 40 percent of the respondents.

It is observed that majority (40%) of the respondents are having 6 to 10 years of experience.

It is noted that majority (60%) of the respondents live in joint family.

Conclusion

Grievances emerge out of the dissatisfaction of workers it may be as an individual or as a group. Grievances are the expressed complaints about

working conditions and environment in which employee work. It is related with day to day work. Nature of grievance may be at individual or at group level, immediate attention and patient hearing from superior is required for amicable industrial relations. Effective grievance handling is an essential part of cultivating good employee relations and running a fair, successful, and productive workplace. It is advisable to set up an effective grievance procedure in the organization. The procedure should be flexible enough to meet the requirements of the organization. It should be simple so that an average employee is able to understand it.

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